

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF DEGREE OF PRONOUN IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation. This article talks about English and Uzbek languages pronouns and their usage. A pronoun is a word used in place of a noun. In modern linguistics, pronouns are of scientific interest, like discourse analysis, text theory, and other fields related to the communicative activity of a person. In the article, we will get acquainted with the role of pronouns in sentence, their type and characteristics.

Key words: Pronoun, classification, role, meaning, Uzbek, English, features, indefiniteness, personal pronouns.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается об этом слове, используемое вместо существительного. В современном языкознании местоимения представляют научный интерес, как анализ дискурса, теория текста и другие области, связанные с коммуникативной деятельностью человека. В статье мы познакомимся с местом местоимений в предложении, их видами и характеристиками.

Ключевые слова: Местоимение, классификация, роль, значение, Узбекский, Английский язык, особенности, определение, личное местоимение.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Ingliz tili va O'zbek tilidagi olmoshlar va ularning qo'llanishi haqida so'z boradi. Olmosh o't o'rnida qo'llanidigan so'zdir. Zamonaviy tilshunoslikda olmosh nutq tahlili, matn nazariyasi va shaxsning muloqot faoliyati bilan bog'liq boshqa sohalar kabi ilmiy qiziqish uyg'otadi. Maqolada olmoshlarning gapdagi o'rnini, uning turlari va xususiyatlari bilan tanishib chiqamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Olmosh, tasnif, rol, ma'nosi, O'zbek, Ingliz xususiyatlari, aniqlik, kishilik olmoshi.

The role of pronouns has always influenced our language by expressing the essence of interpersonal relationships. The goal is to uncover the deeper meaning of the trivial language used by English speakers today. As a result of scientific research on the pronouns used in everyday life, new meaning is added to the words used by students and people. In the article, we will also gain a deeper understanding by studying information about the pronouns used in both languages.

The noun, adjective, number are sometimes used as substitutes for verbs, and the words that refer to the same are called pronouns. ¹Pronoun refers to words used in place of nouns and adjectives. ²The meaning of pronouns is vague and general. Pronouns are distinguished from other word groups by their ambiguity and lack of word formation. ³

¹ Erkaboyeva N. O'zbek tilidan ma'ruzalar to'plami. T.: "Akademnashr", 2014. pp341-346.

² Muhammad G', Qosimova R. Ingliz tili grammatikasi. T.: "Turon Iqbol", 2019. pp158-159.

³ <https://uz.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Olmosh>.

Pronouns in English and Uzbek have a number of distinguishing features. There are also many types of them. They are: Personal pronoun (kishilik olmoshlari), Reflexive pronouns (o'zlik olmoshlari), Reciprocal pronouns (birgalik olmoshlar), Demonstrative pronouns (ko'rsatish olmoshlari), Interrogative pronouns (so'roq olmoshlari), Relative pronoun (nisbiy olmoshlari), Indefinite pronouns (gumon olmoshlari). It is known that the types and names of pronouns are different in both languages. We can see the similarities. In this article, we will discuss only the personal pronouns of the two languages.

"Perhaps **it** doesn't understand English," thought Alice; "It is a French mouse, come over with William the Conqueror." ⁴

U yovvoyi gul edi: dashtda tug'ildi. Bahor yomg'irlari shivirlagan pallada yerni tirmalab, yorug' dunyoga chiqdi.

Personal pronouns are always pronouns, nouns.⁵ Because they refer to one of the three persons, the person or thing that is speaking and being spoken to. As you can see from the examples above, **it** and **u** are personal pronouns in English and Uzbek. But while in English **it** is used for inanimate objects and has its own place and name in the sentence, in Uzbek we see the opposite, that is, **u** is used for one of the three persons.

In conclusion, that English and Uzbek grammar are different from each other. Judging from the correct article, we can say that the names of pronouns in both languages are close to each other. However, their role; function and purpose in the speech are different. We can also observe that personal pronouns are used in one case only for inanimate objects and animals, while in the other case they are also used for persons, things and events. As you can see from the above example, personal pronouns are used differently in both languages.

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⁴ Lewis Carroll. Alice's adventures in wonderland. L.: "Macmillanandco", 1869. pp52

⁵ Muhammad G', Qosimova R. Ingliz tili grammatikasi. T.: "Turon-Iqbol", 2019. pp158